

Fluoberyllates of Trivalent Metals—I Aluminium and Chromic Fluoberyllates and Alums

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A. K. Ghosh and N. Ray¹ isolated $H_2BeF_4 \cdot Cr_2(BeF_4)_3 \cdot 24H_2O$ and its alkali metal salts. They could not, however, prepare the corresponding free chromic and aluminium fluoberyllates. From the properties² of $(AlF_6)^{3-}$ ion and solubility of CaF_2 in solution containing Be^{2+} it appears that $(BeF_4)^{2-}$ is exceptionally stable and the reactions

are feasible in solutions. Thus, $Al_2(BeF_4)_3$ may be formed in preference to the formation of $(AlF_6)^{3-}$ ions. This also may become true, however, for other trivalent metal fluoberyllates. We used fluoberyllic acid³ and the corresponding metal hydroxides as starting materials and this gave satisfactory results. The composition has mainly been established by analytical methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

All reagents used were of A. R. grade.

Methods of analysis: BeF_4^{2-} was determined as $BaBeF_4$ by precipitating with 5% $BaCl_2$ -solution and then heating to a constant weight at 115-120°C.

After precipitation of BeF_4^{2-} ion, Al and Cr were precipitated as their hydroxides, ignited to the oxide and weighed.

In complex chromic fluoberyllates, Be was determined as BeO , fluorine was determined as CaF_2 , after precipitation of Be with dilute ammonia. Cr was then determined as $BaCrO_4$.

Ammonia was estimated by Kjeldahl's method.

Fluoberyllic acid: Fluoberyllic acid was prepared according to the method of Ray *et al.*³.

Aluminium fluoberyllate, $Al_2(BeF_4)_3 \cdot 18H_2O$: A sample of about 2.5 gms. of moist $Al(OH)_3$ was dissolved in conc. H_2BeF_4 . The clear solution had a pH of about 4. This solution on concentration in a vacuum desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 gave transparent crystals which were filtered, washed with alcohol and dried by pressing with filter paper.

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Drying over conc. H_2SO_4 and prolonged exposure in air turned the crystals to white powder hardly soluble in water.

0.1690 gm. of the substance gave 0.1766 gm. of BaBeF_4 and 0.0275 gm. Al_2O_3 . Found, $(\text{BeF}_4)^{2-} = 40.00\%$ and $\text{Al} = 8.61\%$; calculated for $\text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $(\text{BeF}_4)^{2-} = 40.28\%$ and $\text{Al} = 8.53\%$.

Chromic fluoberyllate, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$: A sample of 2.25 gm. of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ was dissolved in conc. H_2BeF_4 . The violet coloured solution thus obtained was concentrated by keeping in a vacuum desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 . The concentrated solution was treated with absolute alcohol in the cold, when violet crystals separated. The crystals could not be dried by pressing between folds of a filter paper, as they were highly deliquescent. They were rapidly filtered through sintered glass crucible, washed thoroughly with absolute alcohol and kept in a desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 .

0.1710 gm. of the violet substance gave 0.1648 gm. of BaBeF_4 and 0.0391 gm. of Cr_2O_3 . Found: $(\text{BeF}_4)^{2-} = 36.90\%$ and $\text{Cr} = 15.64\%$; calculated for $\text{Cr}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $(\text{BeF}_4)^{2-} = 37.32\%$ and $\text{Cr} = 15.08\%$.

Chromic hexammine fluoberyllate pentahydrate, $[\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: 1.2152 gm. of chromic fluoberyllate in aqueous solution was treated with liquor ammonia at 0°C . The colour of the solution gradually changed to violet red. The solution was then filtered from undissolved hydroxides of Cr and Be, and kept in an atmosphere of ammonia over lime in a desiccator. Violet red crystals were obtained which were filtered and dried rapidly in a desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 . The violet red crystals could also be precipitated from solution with absolute alcohol. Yield = 0.4212 gm.

0.1355 gm. of the substance on analysis gave 0.0152 gm. of BeO , 0.0984 gm. of CaF_2 and 0.1070 gm. of BaCrO_4 . Found: $\text{Be} = 4.04\%$, $\text{F} = 35.38\%$ and $\text{Cr} = 16.24\%$; calculated for $(\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_6)_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Be} = 4.13\%$, $\text{F} = 34.92\%$ and $\text{Cr} = 15.92\%$.

Chromic tri-ethylene diamine fluoberyllate trihydrate $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{N} \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_3]_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$: 0.65 gm. of chromic fluoberyllate in aqueous solution was treated with ethylenediamine hydrate at 0° . The colour of the solution gradually changed to deep rose-red. The solution was then filtered from undissolved hydroxides of Be and Cr and kept in a vacuum desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 . The deep red crystals obtained were filtered and quickly dried in a desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 . They could also be obtained from the saturated solution by treatment with absolute alcohol. Yield = 0.3210. The substance was found to be hygroscopic.

0.2226 gm. of the substance gave 0.0216 gm. of BeO , 0.1348 gm. of CaF_2 and 0.1450 gm. of BeCrO_4 . Found, $\text{Be} = 3.50\%$, $\text{F} = 29.95\%$ and $\text{Cr} = 13.39\%$; calculated for $[\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_2\text{—CH}_2\text{—NH}_2)]_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{Be} = 3.49\%$; $\text{Cr} = 13.46\%$ and $\text{F} = 29.49\%$.

Fluoberyllate alums:

Ammonium-Aluminium alum $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$: A sample of 0.125 gm. of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4$ in solution was mixed with 0.633 gm. of aluminium fluoberyllate in

aqueous solution i.e., in molecular proportions(1:1) and kept in a vacuum desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 . Hard transparent crystals obtained were examined under microscope and found to be octahedral in shape. A sample of 0.0795 gm. of the material on analysis gave 0.0847 gm. of $BaBeF_4$ and 0.009 gm. of Al_2O_3 . Found Al=5.99% and BeF_4^{2-} =40.76%; Ammonia was estimated by Kjeldahl's method, % of NH_3 =3.92%; calculated for $(NH_4)_2BeF_4 \cdot Al_2(BeF_4)_3 \cdot 24H_2O$; Al=6.26%, BeF_4^{2-} =39.44% and NH_3 =3.94%.

The same compound was also obtained by digesting 1.21 gm. of ammonium fluoberyllate with about 5 gm. of moist aluminium hydroxide. When the evolution of ammonia ceased, the solution was filtered hot, under suction and the filtrate cooled with ice. Small octahedral crystals were found to appear on cooling.

This compound on analysis was also found to be of composition $(NH_4)_2BeF_4 \cdot Al_2(BeF_4)_3 \cdot 24H_2O$.

The ammonium alum loses its water of crystallisation slowly and the loss in weight corresponds to the loss of nine molecules of water, when kept into desiccator over silica gel.

Potassium-Aluminium alum: $K_2BeF_4 \cdot Al_2(BeF_4)_3 \cdot 24H_2O$: An aqueous solution of 0.165 gm. of potassium fluoberyllate was mixed with 0.633 gm. of aluminium fluoberyllate in solution and crystallised in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulfuric acid. The crystals on examination under microscope were found to be octahedral in shape. A sample of 0.1246 gm. of the material on analysis gave 0.1201 gm. of $BaBeF_4$ and 0.0146 gm. of Al_2O_3 . Found, Al=6.20% and BeF_4^{2-} =36.84%. Calculated for $K_2BeF_4 \cdot Al_2(BeF_4)_3 \cdot 24H_2O$, Al=5.97% and BeF_4^{2-} =37.50%.

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